

LANGUAGE FEATURES OF ADVERTISING SLOGANS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8012662>

Kobilova Aziza Baxriddinovna

a senior teacher, PhD, Bukhara state university

Ruziyeva Dilrabo

1st-year master's student at Bukhara State University

Annotation.

The given article is devoted to the analysis of the structure of advertising text. The main attention is paid to the key phrase of the verbal text of the advertisement - the slogan and lists of the main language that make the slogan expressive.

Keywords.

advertising, slogan, language features, advertising text, languagetechniques, expressive means of the language, expressive syntax, word formation.

In recent decades, the interest of linguists, philologists, psychologists in the study of advertising discourse has increased significantly. Advertising, as a special speech genre, has a significant impact on modern society. This influence is manifested both in the formation of special functional and stylistic phenomena, and in the tendency to change the linguistic personality and the very linguistic picture of the world, which is directly related to changes in the minds of native speakers.

Compared with other areas of mass communication, this feature of the advertising text is especially pronounced. Advertising directly or indirectly interacts with society, and in our work we tried to analyze the language features of advertising slogans. Advertising acts as a complex of many aspects, its development has come a long way, being formed in parallel with the development of society, its globalization and all the positive and negative manifestations associated with it. The advertising text has both economic, informational, social, and linguoculturological and ethno-specific components.

According to scientists, the process of advertising began in ancient times. Advertising researchers (V.L. Muzykant, R.Jay, A.Kornilov, N.Filchikova), trying to find its origins, consider pre-Christian masks used in rituals as a pra-advertising text. V.L. The musician notes that in the period of the pre-market economy, the entire "advertising text was ... on a person, acting as a kind of symbol, a clot of socially significant information that in a certain way positioned the bearer of this

symbolism". O. A. Feofanov in his book USA: Advertising and Society mentions an announcement found by archaeologists in Egypt: "I, Rino from the island of Crete, interpret dreams by the will of the gods." Findings of this kind can rightfully be attributed to the first advertising texts expressing people's desire to advertise themselves, the products of their labor.

In ancient Greece, there was a tradition to mark objects of pottery and art production with a brand name. Ownership signs were also used: the brand was burned not only on domestic animals, but also on slaves. Already in the early stages of cultural development, advertising begins to appear in the form of a written text. However, some authors (for example, E.V. Salnikova) notice that in such advertising there is still no self-awareness of the advertising industry and an inner sense of advertising as an independent phenomenon. "There is no ambition of irresistible impact, no aplomb of creating a prestigious sphere at the intersection of commerce and culture".

Other researchers of advertising and advertising text are inclined to assert that the developed advertising activity began only with the birth of printing, i.e. not earlier than the middle of the 15th century. In our opinion, it is difficult to agree with this opinion. Evidence of this is the abundance and functional variety of advertising items, the wealth of techniques and means inherent in ancient advertising.

A huge number of specialists work on advertising texts: philologists and linguists, copywriters and psychologists. The minimum amount of advertising text should be the maximum amount of memorable and convincing information presented by ethical, grammatical rules and norms meeting the requirements of the International Code of Advertising Practice. The structure of the advertising text deserves special attention. It consists of a ktemothenism (a verbal component of a trademark), a slogan, a commentary part and details (addresses and phone numbers of the manufacturer or distributor of goods).

Slogan (from the English slogan - "slogan, motto") - the key phrase of the verbal text of advertising. Its main purpose is to attract attention and encourage action.

The expressive means listed below can make the slogan as interesting and memorable as possible:

The use of phraseological units: ORIFLAME, mascara. Your lashes are top-notch. NIVEA Visage. Take time into your own hands. ALERANA hair strengthening spray. So that happiness does not hang by a thread. Some catchwords and expressions used in advertising can be interpreted somewhat

differently. For example, favorite ice cream since childhood or may there always be a holiday.

Sound writing: alliteration and assonance. A selection of sound combinations in the slogan conveys sound sensations that arise in the process of using one or another advertised products: "Melts in your mouth, not in your hands" by M&Ms, "Finger-lickin' good" by KFC, "Snap, Crackle, Pop" by Rice Krispies.

Use of metaphors: ORIFLAME, lipstick. The energy of the stars on your lips.

Comparison: Ice cream "Magnate Gold". More expensive than gold.

Hyperbole: "The best a man can get". (Gillette), the mattress will make you sleep like a baby.

Repetition: SUNSILK hair care product. Change style. Change the world. Talosto. Live ice cream from live milk.

Pun: Shave time. Shave money.

Antithesis: "Everybody doesn't like something, but nobody doesn't like Sara Lee." - Sara Lee advertising campaign.

Parallelism: easy to buy, easy to install, easy to expand or a different kind of company. A different kind of car.

Abbreviations are used in the texts to increase the informative content of the text and save advertising space. The authors of advertising slogans turn to the use of abbreviations to prove that the advertised product was carefully developed and tested and highly qualified specialists took part in its creation: **AIDA (Attention, Interest, Desire, Action)** It is a four-step purchase funnel where customers travel from attention to action. **B2C (Business to Customer)** The communication between a customer and a business

Jargon: click-throughs and page views.

With the purpose of making the advertising phrase more harmonious in phonetic or graphic terms, spelling errors are sometimes deliberately used: Ohdeer it is hard to spel when your hungry. If you keap making typing mistakes grab yourself a snickers fast.

The syntax of advertising texts is simple, as it is designed for quick perception. The dominance of a simple sentence is explained by the desire to formulate the slogan and the commentary part of the advertising text as briefly and clearly as possible: Creamy ice cream "Soviet". Truly creamy! Taste of childhood.

Some language techniques are used in advertising texts quite often. Sometimes in advertising messages there are sentences highlighted with the help of a special text parceling. Such packaged constructions are built according to the following principle: in the first sentence, a product is called with a noun, and in the

subsequent ones, representing its characteristics, there are verbs and adjectives-predicates correlated with this noun (for example, Sanorin. Quickly eliminates nasal congestion. Reduces swelling of the nasal mucosa. Provides high efficiency due to modern dosage form. Effective and safe). Parceling belongs to the realm of expressive syntax.

Often used appeals and incentive constructions. The use of interrogative and exclamatory sentences (a question-answer form of presentation) emphasizes the "inviting" tone of advertising (for example, VICHY Lipo Metric, -shaping product. Do you really want to lose weight? You need a product whose body effectiveness has been proven. CLINIQUE, products for cleansing, exfoliating, and skin hydration. Can you create great skin? Yes. Say yes to great skin).

Verbal nouns are often used to describe the services offered in advertising (eg, Oftalmoferon. Treatment of viral and allergic eye diseases; LaStrada. Photorejuvenation. Photoepilation).

Advertising can be addressed to one person or a group of people. The form of appeal depends on what product is advertised. The age of the potential buyer must also be taken into account. As a rule, a respectful appeal to you is used, addressing you is acceptable in advertising for "youth" products and means a transition to more confidential communication (for example, Sundae "Mood". Share your mood! Ice cream "Maxibon". Turn on life to the maximum!).

The advertising text must prove the superiority of the promoted product. Advertisers try to distinguish their product from the crowd by using words with prefixes super-, hyper-, mega-, as well as adjectives that are close in meaning to the word most: amazing, unique, outstanding, exclusive, etc.

The language of advertising should be bright, so the authors of advertising texts use a huge wealth of Russian vocabulary and phraseology, expressive possibilities, word formation, grammatical features of parts of speech, and syntactic figures. The language of advertising can be called a special sub-style, formed at the junction of official business and journalistic styles, in demand and rapidly developing.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Brierley, S. (1995). The Advertising Handbook. Routledge
2. Goddard, A (1998) The Language of Advertising. Routledge: New York
3. <http://www.rjelal.com/5.4.17a/309-15%20Dr.%20T.%20RAJA%20SEKHAR.pdf>

4. <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/downArticle/493/5/1/180066>
5. <https://repository.sustech.edu/bitstream/handle/123456789/23931/Analyzing%20Linguistic%20Features%20....pdf?sequence=1>
6. Kobilova, A. B. (2016). Peer editing as a main technique in editing writing. International scientific journal, (4 (2)), 37-38. [http://www.irbis-nbu.gov.ua/cgi-bin/irbis_nbu/cgiirbis_64.exe?C21COM=2&I21DBN=UJRN&P21DBN=UJRN&IMAGE_FILE_DOWNLOAD=1&Image_file_name=PDF/mnj_2016_4\(2\)_11.pdf](http://www.irbis-nbu.gov.ua/cgi-bin/irbis_nbu/cgiirbis_64.exe?C21COM=2&I21DBN=UJRN&P21DBN=UJRN&IMAGE_FILE_DOWNLOAD=1&Image_file_name=PDF/mnj_2016_4(2)_11.pdf)
7. Kobilova A.B. Periphrasis used in medical texts. Proceeding of International Conference on Research Innovation In Multidisciplinary Sciences, Hosted From New York USA 6th -7th of March, 2021. – Page: 261-262. <https://papers.econferenceglobe.com/index.php/ecg/article/view/101>
8. Baxriddinova, K. A. (2022). Voqelik obyektini perifrastik sinonimlar orqali ifodalash. Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes, 71–73. Retrieved from <http://www.conferenceseries.info/index.php/online/article/view/47>
9. Kobilova A.B. Инглиз ва ўзбек лингвомаданиятида тиббий перифразаларнинг хусусиятлари: филология фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори (PhD) диссертацияси.– Бухоро, 2022. – 148-б.;
10. Kobilova, A. B. (2016). Peer editing as a main technique in editing writing. International scientific journal, (4 (2)), 37-38. <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=32733619>
11. Kobilova Aziza Baxriddinova (2023). THE FORMATION OF MEDICAL PERIPHRASES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES | Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities <http://farspublishers.org/index.php/ijessh/article/view/523>
12. Baxriddinova, K. A. (2023). The Role of Medical Periphrases in the Semantic Micro- Field of English Language. Miasto Przyszłości, 32, 155–160. Retrieved from <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1119>
13. Kobilova, A. B. (2017). Different types of tests used in language teaching. Міжнародний науковий журнал Інтернаука, (1 (1)), 134-135. <https://www.inter-nauka.com/issues/2017/1/1898>
14. KA Baxriddinova. Characteristic features of euphemistic periphrases. Vol. 3 No. 29 (2023): Innovation in the modern education system

<https://interonconf.org/index.php/usa/article/view/3885>

15. Кобилова А.Б. Анализ перифраз используемых вместо различных лекарственных растений (на материале английского и узбекского языков).

Том 4 № 1-1 (2021): международный журнал искусство слова.

<https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/art/article/view/383>

16. Kobilova Aziza Bakhridinovna. Some considerations about periphrases // *Academicia: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*. ISSN (Online): 2249-7137, Vol.11, Issue 2, 30-February 2021. –P. 1637-1640. (Impact Factor (SJIF. 2021) – 7.492).

<https://www.indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:aca&volume=11&issue=2&article=264>

17. Kobilova Aziza Bakhridinovna. The use of the medical periphrases of the Uzbek and English languages in journalistic texts // *JournalNX: A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal*. ISSN (Online): 2581-4230, Vol.7, Issue 6, 30-June 2021. –P. 143–150. (Impact Factor (SJIF. 2021) – 7.22).

<https://www.neliti.com/publications/347772/the-use-of-the-medical-periphrases-of-the-uzbek-and-english-languages-in-journal>

18. Kobilova A.B. Lingua-cultural aspects of medical periphrases of English language // *Academicia: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*. ISSN (Online): 2249-7137, Vol.12, Issue 05, 30-May 2022. P. 15-20.

https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/6099

19. Kobilova Aziza Bakhridinovna. Semantic and lingua-cultural features of English and Uzbek medical periphrases // *International Journal on Integrated Education*. ISSN (Online): 2620-3502, Vol.5, Issue 6, 6-June 2022. P. 162-167.

<https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJIE/article/view/3144>

20. Kobilova A.B. Periphrases used in medical texts and their characteristics (on the example of english and uzbek languages) // *Proceedings of Global Technovation 4th International Multidisciplinary Scientific Conference*. – Paris, France, 2021. – P. 255-257.

<https://conferencepublication.com/index.php/aoc/article/view/740>